

Design and implementation of two-dimensional digital finite impulse response filter using very high speed integrated circuit hardware description language

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ABSTRACT

The main purpose of this paper is to design a two-dimensional digital finite impulse response (FIR) filter using data broadcast and non-broadcast structure. The implementation of two-dimensional digital FIR filter is done using very high speed integrated circuit hardware description language (VHDL). Rectangular window method is used for calculating 2D digital FIR filter coefficients for data broadcast and non-broadcast structure. The coefficients of the one-dimensional digital FIR filter are obtained using the MATLAB filter design and analysis (FDA) tool for two different cut-off frequencies and are multiplied to get the necessary coefficient for the two-dimensional FIR filter to be designed; the simulation is done on Artix-7 series field programmable gate array (FPGA), target device (xc7a35t-cpg236) using Vivadov.2015.2. The proposed design reduces the area utilization and the power consumption when compared with the existing literature. The experimental result shows that the power consumption is improved by 97% and there is an improvement of 24% in area utilization for the two-dimensional with and without data broadcast one dimensional FIR filter structures.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Due to the recent advancement in the techniques of designing digital finite impulse response (FIR) filters, filters with low power consumption and area efficient are of major concerned. Such optimized filters can be designed using all the techniques available with recent developments. One such technique i.e. data broadcast, provides lesser area utilization and less power consumption when compare with the conventional filter design methods [1]. The main parameter of a device is the power consumption and area. Device with less power consumption and less area are more recognition and more preferable and implementation of such devices are highly recommended. So in order to meet this requirement of devices, the filters present in them are to be made accordingly. Digital filters in such devices may be FIR or infinite impulse response (IIR), but mostly FIR is more preferable. In order to optimize, techniques like parallel processing, pipelining, and data broadcast structure design are widely in practiced [2]. Digital signal processing applications opted for the above techniques whichever is suitable for the particular application. Two-dimensional digital FIR filters and their respective design methods are widely in development because of its importance in digital signal processing applications that inherently involved two-dimensional signals. A new technique known as hybrid encoding was proposed in [3], this method makes use of hybrid operators in the architecture of FIR which

reduces the power consumption by 25% with 14% delay improvement with the penalty area of 28%. Mitra [4] and Babu [5] explain that FIR filter architecture with hybrid encoding covers a larger area but it compensates with the clock delay and energy per sample.

Digital filter implemented using a cascade arrangement was proposed in [6]. In this method, to design a multi section filter, cascading of various low order sections was done and switching of current input signal is made by using a simple adaptation mechanism which in turn minimizes the power consumption. An efficient way of hardware implementation of FIR filter on FPGA was proposed in [7], [8]. In this paper, the filter specifications were obtained from the MATLAB filter design and analysis (FDA) tool. Very high speed integrated circuit hardware description language (VHDL) hardware description language was used; it fully supports all the binary and arithmetic multiplication which suits for this design.

Phuong [9] proposed the design of digital FIR filter using window technique. With all the windowing techniques available, Rectangular window method was adopted in this paper which has the advantage of trading off the transition and ripple. With the advancement in the technology and the desire of improvement, filter which enhances the speed of the system is highly on demand. Kamaraj *et al.* [10] proposed the design of FIR filters using hardware description language (HDL). In order to optimize the utilization of hardware, the technique of pipelining method was adopted. By adopting this technique, multiple numbers of instructions can be overlapped in the execution process which improves the speed of the operation and ultimately increases the speed of the system thereby delaying the critical path delay.

Hu and Rabiner [11]–[13] present the different techniques that can be adopted for designing two dimensional digital filters. The filter can be designed by using either frequency sampling or optimal design methods whichever is suitable for the desire filter specifications with a considerable amount of computational cost. The conventional McClellan transformation technique is used for designing 2D filter varying 2D variable [2]. The cut-off frequency is used as the orbit function for determining the sub filter specifications and the 1D prototype variable can be designed and can be adjusted using the same variable. 2D filter design can be initiated from a specified 1D prototype filter and transforming its transfer function using different frequency mappings in order to obtain a 2D filter with the desired frequency response [14], [15]. Mohanty and Meher [16] states that filter design using data broadcast structure offers higher speed of operation and less area utilization, while 2D filter design without data broadcast structure also optimizes the above mentioned parameters with less critical path delay.

2. DESIGNING OF TWO-DIMENSIONAL FIR FILTER USING TWO 1-D FIR FILTER

The general equation of a 1-D digital FIR filter is expressed as in (1) [17]:

$$y(n) = \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} h(k)x(n-k) \quad (1)$$

where n is the length of the filter. Two dimensional FIR filter equation is expressed as in (2) [18].

$$y(n_1, n_2) = \sum_{k_1} \sum_{k_2} h(k_1 k_2)x(n_1 - k_1, n_2 - k_2) \quad (2)$$

To design a low pass digital FIR filter, MATLAB FDA tool is used as the synthesis tool with the specifications given in the Table 1 and the corresponding transfer function will have the coefficients as shown in Table 2.

Table 1. Filter specifications for $w_1(n_1)$ and $w_2(n_2)$

Properties	Specifications	
	$w_1(n_1)$	$w_2(n_2)$
Response	Low pass	Low pass
Order	2	2
Structure	Direct Form I	Direct Form I
Window	Rectangular window	Rectangular window
Cut-off frequency (ω_c)	0.5 (normalized)	0.7(normalized)
Filter length	3	3
Frequency Specification	(0-1 normalized)	(0-1 normalized)
Number of multipliers	3	3
Number of adders	2	2
Number of states	2	2
Multiplications per input sample	3	3
Additions per input sample	2	2

Table 2. Filter coefficients from MATLAB FDA tool for $w_1(n_1)$ and $w_2(n_2)$

Transfer function	Coefficient $w_1(n_1)$	Coefficient $w_2(n_2)$
$h(0)$	0.280	0.211
$h(1)$	0.439	0.576
$h(2)$	0.280	0.211

2.1. Simulation results of MATLAB FDA tool

Magnitude and phase response for $w_1(n_1)$ and $w_2(n_2)$ are shown in Figures 1 to 4. These figures illustrates the magnitude and phase responses obtained in FDA tool for different values of $w_1(n_1)$ and $w_2(n_2)$. Magnitude responses for $w_1(n_1)=0.5$ and $w_1(n_2)=0.7$ are shown in Figures 1 and 2, while the phase responses for $w_1(n_1)=0.5$ and $w_1(n_2)=0.7$ are shown in Figures 3 and 4. The 1-D FIR filter is designed using rectangular window and the corresponding parameters are also obtained. For rectangular window, the expression is given in (3) as mentioned by [19]–[21].

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & 0 \leq n \leq M \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \tag{3}$$

Figure 1. Magnitude response for $w_1(n_1)=0.5$

Figure 2. Magnitude response for $w_2(n_2)=0.7$

Figure 3. Phase response for $w_1(n_1)=0.5$

Figure 4. Phase response for $w_2(n_2)=0.7$

3. 2-DIMENSIONAL FILTER COEFFICIENT CALCULATION

For rectangular R, the window is formed as an outer product of two 1-D windows by using the formula [18].

$$wR(n1, n2) = w1(n1) * w2(n2) \tag{4}$$

The coefficient of the two-dimensional filter can also be obtained using the formula (4) with the 1D coefficient obtained from the FDA tool as shown in (5).

$$\begin{bmatrix} a_0 \\ a_1 \\ a_2 \end{bmatrix} * \begin{bmatrix} a_0 \\ a_1 \\ a_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a_{00} & a_{01} & a_{02} \\ a_{10} & a_{11} & a_{12} \\ a_{20} & a_{21} & a_{22} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0.280 \\ 0.439 \\ 0.280 \end{bmatrix} * \begin{bmatrix} 0.211 \\ 0.576 \\ 0.211 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.059 & 0.092 & 0.092 \\ 0.161 & 0.252 & 0.161 \\ 0.059 & 0.092 & 0.059 \end{bmatrix} \tag{5}$$

4. REALIZATION OF DATA BROADCAST AND NON-BROADCAST FINITE IMPULSE RESPONSE FILTER STRUCTURES

Digital FIR filter design using data broadcast structure does not need the introduction of any pipelining latches instead it transposes the original structure of the filter and reduces the critical path delay which lead to broadcasting of the data to all the multipliers simultaneously instead of storing the data [22]. The basic concept of signal flow graph is used to know the characteristics of the filter [23], [24]. Figure 5 represents the flow graph for a 3-tap FIR filter and Figure 6 represents the transposed signal flow graph of the 3-tap FIR filter. The general form of 1D digital FIR filters with data broadcast and non-broadcast structures are shown in the Figures 7 and 8. Two dimensional digital FIR filters with and without data broadcast structures are proposed and compare them with the existing architectures.

Figure 5. Signal flow graph of FIR filter

Figure 6. Transposed signal flow graph (SFG) of the FIR filter

Figure 7. Data broadcast structure of a 1D 3-tap FIR filter

Figure 8. Non-broadcast structure of a 1D 3-tap FIR filter

5. IMPLEMENTATION OF TWO DIMENSIONAL FIR FILTER

A novel architecture of two dimensional FIR filter with data non-broadcast structure is proposed in this paper. FIR filter design using this technique improves the speed of operation considerably when compare to the existing architectures. Also, it shows a reduced critical path delay when a filter with data broadcast structure set aside. But there is a trade-off between these architectures, as the area and the power consume by this architecture is slightly increased, which can be neglected as compare to the other existing ones. The two dimensional digital FIR filter without data broadcast structure is shown in the Figure 9.

A 3 tap two-dimensional digital FIR filter of order 2 without data broadcast is designed using Vivado 2015.2 with the coefficients obtained from the FDA tool in MATLAB. The structure offers a reduced critical path delay, but the design consumes more power and area because of the extra pipelining latches present. The data broadcast structure of two dimensional FIR filter is shown in Figure 10. In this structure, the data is being broadcasted to all the multipliers simultaneously without using any pipelining latches which ultimately saves the area and power. This type architecture also reduces the critical path delay thereby reducing the delay of the device.

FIR filter design with this method improves the speed of the device as a whole. Hence, digital FIR filter with the adoption of this technique saves power, area and improves the speed of the operation without any unwanted delay. When comparing with the existing architectures available for FIR filter, filter designed using data broadcast structure shows a drastic reduction in the area occupancy, power consumption and critical path delay. A 3 tap two-dimensional digital FIR filter design with data broadcast structure compensates the critical path delay in terms of power and area. FIR filter with data broadcast structure improves the power consumption and the area.

Figure 9. Two-dimensional FIR filter without data broadcast structure

Figure 10. Two-dimensional FIR filter with data broadcast structure

6. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The register transfer level (RTL) schematic diagram of the proposed two-dimensional FIR filter with and without data broadcast structures are shown in the Figures 11 and 12. Figure 11 shows the RTL schematic of two-dimensional FIR filter without data broadcast and Figure 12 shows the RTL schematic of two-dimensional FIR filter with data broadcast structure.

Figure 11. RTL schematic diagram of 2D FIR filter without data broadcast structure

Figure 12. RTL schematic diagram of 2D FIR filter with data broadcast structure

7. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

The Table 3 shows the results of the proposed two-dimensional with data broadcast structure and non-data broadcast structure. The novel architectures proposed in this paper consumes only 0.169 W and 0.183 W respectively with the area utilization of only 39 LUTs out of 20800 available which is only 0.19% of the total available resource. The speed or the critical path delay is also reduced for non-data broadcast structure with only 7.332 ns and 7.465 ns for data broadcast structure. Table 3 shows synthesis results of the implemented filters, it is clear that two-dimensional FIR filter with data broadcast structure consumes very low power when compare it with the FIR filter without data broadcast structure. There is a trade off in the critical path delay, which means there is a slight increase in the delay for the data broadcast structure.

Table 3. Synthesis results for implemented 2D FIR filter

Proposed Structures	Power (Watt)	Area(LUT)	Speed(ns)
2D data broadcast FIR digital filter structure	0.169W	39 LUT (0.19%)	7.465
2D non-broadcast FIR digital filter structure	0.183W	39 LUT (0.19%)	7.332

Table 4 is a comparison table of the proposed architectures and the existing architectures. From the Table 4, it can be seen that the power consumed by the proposed architecture is being reduce in a considerable amount up to 0.169 W and 0.182 W or data broadcast and non-data broadcast structures of FIR filter respectively. The amount of power consumed by the existing architectures is from 15 to 34 Watts. So, it is clear that there is a significant improvement in the proposed novel architecture with 97% improvement in terms of power consumption. Table 4 also compares the proposed architectures and the existing architectures in terms of area utilization. The area utilized by the proposed novel architecture is only 39 LUTs out of the 20800 available, which is only 0.19% of the total resource available. But, the existing architectures utilize 52 to 77 LUTs out of the total 20800 available. The improvement is 24% in terms of area utilization.

Table 5 is the comparison of the proposed novel architectures and the existing architectures in terms of critical path delay. The proposed architectures show a significant reduction in the critical path delay with values 7.456 ns and 7.332 ns. There is an improvement of 57% when compared with the [13]. The simulated output waveform for the proposed two-dimensional FIR filter with and without data broadcast structures is shown in Figure 13.

Table 4. Comparison between the existing and the proposed design in terms of area and power consumption

Device used	Power (Watt)	Area Utilization in LUT (%)
Artix-7 (xc7a200tfbg676)(speed grade-1) [18]	FIR 3 tap filter 15.152	FIR 3 tap filter 38 out of 133800
	Parallel-pipeline FIR filter 8.053	Parallel-pipeline FIR filter 21 out of 133800
Virtex-4 (XC4VFX12) [16]	--	Serial FIR filter Pipelined FIR filter 6 6
Virtex-5 (XC5VLX110T) [16]	--	Serial FIR filter Pipelined FIR filter 1 1
Virtex-6 (XC6VCX75T) [16]	--	Serial FIR filter Pipelined FIR filter 1 1
Artix-7 (xc7a200tfbg676)(speed grade-1) [25]	2-parallel 3-tap FIR filter 24.359	2-parallel 3-tap FIR filter 0.25
	2-unfolded 3-tap FIR filter 22.857	2-unfolded 3-tap FIR filter 0.25
	3-parallel 3-tap FIR filter 34.928	3-parallel 3-tap FIR filter 0.36
	3-unfolded 3 tap FIR filter 34.3978	3-unfolded 3 tap FIR filter 0.37
Proposed Structure (Artix-7) (xc7a35t-cpg236)	3-tap Data broadcast 0.169	3-tap Data broadcast 0.19
	3-tap non-Data broadcast 0.183	3-tap non-Data broadcast 0.19

Table 5. Comparison between the existing and the proposed design in terms of delay

Structures	Delay (ns)	
16 bit Vedic multiplier [17]	4-tap micro-programmed sequential FIR filter 10.56 ns	4-tap micro-programmed parallel FIR filter 14.28 ns
16 bit Wallace tree multiplier [17]	4-tap micro-programmed sequential FIR filter 15.56 ns	4-tap micro-programmed parallel FIR filter 19.51 ns
Virtex-4 (XC4VFX12) [18]	Serial FIR filter 24.648 ns	Pipelined FIR filter 22.012 ns
	Serial FIR filter 18.696 ns	Pipelined FIR filter 15.928 ns
Virtex-5 (XC5VLX110T) [18]	Serial FIR filter 17.411 ns	Pipelined FIR filter 15.456 ns
	3-tap FIR filter 9.347 ns	
Artix-7 (xc7a200tfbg676) (speed grade-1) [26]		
Proposed Structure (Artix-7) (xc7a35t-cpg236)	2D Data broadcast FIR filter 7.456 ns	2D Non Broadcast FIR filter 7.332 ns

Figure 13. Simulated output waveform for 2D FIR filter

8. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we designed and implemented a two dimensional digital FIR filters with and without data broadcast structures. Synthesis and simulation are carried out in Artix-7 series with target device (xc7a35t-cpg236) using Vivavdo v2015.2. Data broadcast structure of digital FIR filters improves the area by using only 39 LUTs of the 20800 available i.e 0.19% of the total resource and the power consumption by this method is only 0.169 W. On the other hand, digital FIR filter without data broadcast structure also utilizes 39 LUTs of the 20800 available i.e. 0.21% of the total resource with the power consumption of 0.183 W. The critical path delay is also reduced significantly when these techniques are adopted with 7.456 ns and 7.332 ns respectively. With these results, two-dimensional digital FIR filters design with and without data broadcast structures offers an optimized version of the filter when comparing with the existing conventional architecture.

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